

Negotiating Nationalism: Gandhian Hegemony & Tribal Society in Maharashtra

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Abstract:

This paper examines the relation between Gandhian nationalism and tribal communities in Maharashtra through the analytical framework of Gramsci's Hegemony. The study argued that Gandhian leadership functioned as a form of ideological hegemony grounded in consent rather than force. Drawing the Antonio Gramsci's ideas – such as Satyagraha, Constructive programme, use of Khadi- Self-reliance, liquor prohibition and civil disobedience, non-cooperation – were communicated and adapted Gandhian ideals within tribal regions of Maharashtra. Using district wise evidence from the Civil Disobedience Movement, Particularly from tribal concentration areas such as West Khandesh, East Khandesh, Nashik, Nanded, Palghar and Chandrapur. The study highlights the role of local leaders and volunteers as intermediaries in spreading Gandhian ideology. It indicate that tribal participation was fostered through ethical persuasion and voluntary discipline rather than polical compulsion or force. Activities such as village meetings, liquor picketing, and khadi promotion contributed to reshaping everyday social behavior. The further argues that tribal engagement with Gandhian nationalism was not mere passive but active through adaptation. Through the application of Hegemony as a historical tool, this study offers a nuanced understanding of Nationalist movement in Maharashtra and highlights tribal communities as active agent in the making of the Indian national movement.

Keywords: *Hegemony, Gandhian Hegemony, Tribal district in Maharashtra, M.K. Gandhi.*

Introduction:

The Indian National Movement under the leadership in Mahatma Gandhi transformed the character of anti-colonial struggle by bringing large sections of Indian society into active political participation. In Maharashtra where a significant tribal population lived, the encounter between Gandhian nationalism and tribal society assumed crucial historical form. Tribal societies in Maharashtra have their own cultural practices, organization and authority long before the advent of nationalist politics. Tribal resistance during Freedom Struggle may be understood in three phases: During the moderate phase of the Indian National Movement (1885-1905) their protests were against local moneylenders, British Forest

policies like encroachment on land, forest use restriction. These struggles remained localized in nature. In the Extremist phase (1905-1919) tribals increasingly challenged colonial forest policies. Despite this growing intensity, in this phase tribal movement remained fragmented because of lacking unifying political ideology. A transformation occurred in the Gandhian phase (1920-1947) when Mahatma Gandhi introduced new dimension of resistance. This phase marked shift from localized resistance to participation in broader National Movement. It emerged through negotiation, adaptation, and consent shaped by social & cultural contexts. This paper argues that Gandhian influence among tribals societies in Maharashtra can understood through the concept

of Hegemony, interpreted as moral & ideological leadership based consent rather than force. Gandhi's leadership did not rely on force it operated through ethical appeal- Satyagraha. By using hegemony as a historical tool, this study examines how Gandhian ideas were interpreted, communicated and practiced within tribals in Maharashtra.

Importance of tribal societies in Maharashtra:

Maharashtra has one of the largest concentrations of schedule tribes in India. In accordance with 2011 census report the total tribal population in Maharashtra state is 105.10 lakh and state ranks 2nd in the country for the total tribal population.¹ This substantial demographic of Tribal communities are crucial stakeholder in state.

The Panchayat Provisions (Extension to Scheduled Areas) Act 1996, enacted in 10 states of the country according to this act Scheduled areas of Maharashtra included 13 District, 59 Taluka and 6000 Pesa villages in 2895 GramPanchayats.²

Scheduled Areas in Maharashtra³

Hegemony as Historical Tool:

Hegemony is a multidisciplinary concept used as an analytical tool in History, Political theory, cultural studies and sociology. Hegemony can be effectively used as a historical tool to analyses forms of power and leadership that operate through ideas, consent and moral

authority rather than force. According to Antonio Gramsci Hegemony is leadership based on consent, moral Authority and spread of ideas rather than force.⁴ Mahatma Gandhi's leadership fits in this idea.

Gandhian Hegemony and Tribes in Maharashtra (District based):

1. Leadership through consent: Gandhian Hegemony:

In the context of the Indian Freedom Movement, Gandhian ideas exemplify hegemonic leadership. Gandhi did not rely on force to mobilize people. Instead his leadership rested on moral principles such as Ahimsa, Satya, Self-reliance and social reform. Through practices like Constructive Programme, Satyagraha, and Promoting self-reliance- Khadi and prohibition campaign Gandhi created a framework that encouraged social participation.

Gandhi's **Constructive programme** and Tribes in Maharashtra: According to Mahatma Gandhi the constructive programme aimed to achieve Swaraj by transforming society through village based non- violent work. From a Gramscian perspective this programme is form of Hegemony. In his discussion of tribal societies, Mahatma Gandhi clarifies that the term Adivasi-Raniparaj derived from Kaliparaj was used for local tribal population coined by Shri Jugatram while the term Adivasi- Original inhabitants was popularized by Thakkar Bapa to refer the communities like Bhil, Gond, hills tribes. Gandhi included the service of Adivasis as a crucial component of the Constructive Programme. He argued that India's vast diversity made national unity impossible unless every social unit developed a living consciousness of belonging to a single nation. He cited the pioneer work of Jugatram Dave, Thakkar Bapa, Balasaheb Kher-President of Adivasi Seva Mandal 1940.⁵ In Gramscian concept, Gandhi's treatment of

Adivasi reflects intellectual and moral leadership, not by force. By redefining Tribals through term like Adivasi, Gandhi reshaped social consciousness. He tried to integrate marginal groups into a broader nationalist view. This is a classic case of Hegemonic leadership through consent.

Mahatma Gandhi argued that the wellbeing of each individual is inseparable from the welfare for all. Expressing this principle as both moral frameworks for equitable society.⁶ In the tribal context, philosophy of **Sarvodaya** that is the upliftment of all, thus concept often used as **Antyodaya** emphasizing the rise of last and marginalized section of society.

From a Gramscian perspective, Gandhi's concept of **Sarvodaya** represented to build hegemony through moral persuasion. Within tribal society, Antyodaya provide ethical principle into a locally intelligible framework that allows marginal communities to engage with national movement through moral consent rather than coercion.

According to Vinay Kumar Shrivastava – the director of anthropological survey of India, Kolkata. He argued that Gandhi was influenced by self-reliance of tribals. He adopted the concept of Swaraj & Khadi by the influence of the tribals self-reliance.⁷ Viewed through the lens of hegemony Gandhi drawn the element of self-reliance from Tribals life, rather than imposing ideas upon tribals.

2. Local tribal leaders and volunteers as an ideology carriers:

Gandhian leadership was not based on formal political authority like colonial rule, which dependent on laws, police, and coercion. While Gandhi insistence on Satya-Truth and Ahimsa-Non Violence create trust among marginalized communities that is tribal societies. This moral credibility encouraged voluntary participation rather than forcefully obedience. Evidence from

the Civil Disobedience Movement in Maharashtra reflects that Gandhian leadership Functioned through local intermediaries. Meetings conducted across districts were addressed by regional leaders and volunteers who propagated Gandhian ideas. During April to September 1930 extensive nationalist mobilization was reported in several districts.⁸ But here I use only districts where tribal population is concentrated.

Eg. In **West Khandesh**, on 29 March 1930 a meeting was held at Shirpur under the presidentship of Shankar Parashram Joshi. The meeting was attended by approximately 250-300 people. Speakers such as Shankar Vinayak Thakar from Mukhi in Shindkheda taluka and Balkisan Lakmidas Mehta-Balubhai from Nandurbar advocated khadi, opposition to the salt tax, participation in Gandhian civil disobedience movement. This indicating consent based mass mobilization rather than force.⁹

In **East Khandesh**, 8 meetings were conducted, on 30 May 1930 attendance figures including around 1000 participant at Jalgaon and approx.. 800 at Erandol.¹⁰

In the **Nashik** district, a total of 9 nationalist meetings were reported during 1930, 4 meetings held in Nashik itself. The largest gathering recorded on 6 April 1930 attracted an audience of approx... 2000 participants.¹¹ In **Nasik** district 12 meeting were organized. 3 meetings at Satana recorded people attendance are 500, and 2 meetings at Yeola drew audiences of approx.. 1500 and 800, in this meeting held on 23 May was linked with forest satyagrahas at Sangamner and the demand for Swaraj.¹²

On 31 March 1939, 47 satyagrahis from Pusad participated in a Satyagraha at Kothala in the Hadgaon Police Station area of **Nanded** District. And 2nd Satyagraha on 14 April 1939, when 77 satyagrahis from Pusad again offered protest at the same location.¹³

This examples indicating wide diffusion of Gandhian Ideology. The district wise evidences reflect the operation of Gandhian hegemony through mass consent and decentralized leadership. Large Voluntary gathering, meetings and active involvement of locals especially in tribal districts of Maharashtra.

3. Voluntary Discipline as a tool of consent: khadi, satyagrahas, prohibiting liquor:

Practices such as Khadi- self-reliance, participating nonviolent protest that is Satyagrahas and Picketing liquor, Tribal Participation in such practices reflects a conscious acceptance of Gandhian ethical principles and ideals rather than obedience to imposed authority.

The practice of liquor picketing & appeals to toddy contractors reflect attempts to transform behavior through ethical principles instead of force.

In **Palghar** Chholalal Ramdas Shroff has taken part in picketing liquor during Civil Disobedience movement. At Nargol, in Dahanu Taluka, a meeting was held under the M.M. Karbhai, in this meeting approx.. 125 persons were present. During the meeting, toddy contractor were advised to abstain from participating in Government auctions. Report indicate that futgudi tribal groups and various castes were specially invited to take an active interest in the national movement.¹⁴ this evidence indicate that local leaders and volunteers acted as intermediaries in Gandhian idea at grassroots level.

M.S. Ane was actively engaged in organizing Forest Satyagraha as a form of peaceful protest against forest laws in the **Yeotmal** district, and gives the Government a 15 days' notice before the campaign. This advance notice reflected the Gandhian ideas of Ahimsa-Nonviolence. It shows exercise of moral authority rather than forceful challenge.¹⁵

On 2 May 1930, a public meeting held in **Chanda**[#] under Khushalchand and the principal speaker was Nilkanthrao Deshmukh of Viral in Wardha district. He criticized the audience for continued use of foreign cloth and seeking redress from colonial officials. He argued the public to place complete trust in Mahatma Gandhi. Indicates Gandhian moral leadership functioned as a hegemonic force within the National movement. Khushalchand outlined a strategic reorientation of national activity from urban centers towards in the village. Underlining the importance of rural areas in broadening the movement's social base. He noted the shortage of volunteers in the district and appeal for greater participation in the nationalist cause.¹⁶ In tribal regions of Maharashtra, national volunteers operated as 'organic intellectuals'* by interpreting Gandhian principles through meetings, silent protest, Satyagraha etc.

Conclusion:

The finding shows that Gandhian volunteers, constructive workers and local leaders functioned as organic intellectuals who spread nationalist ideas of Gandhi such as Nonviolence-Ahimsa, Sarvodaya, Antyodaya, and self-reliance. Through village meetings, prohibition campaigns, Khadi promotion and constructive programme, these actors imparted nationalist value within tribal communities. Folk songs and local participation reveal how tribals got influenced by Gandhian ideas. Reflecting active adaptation rather than passive reception.

By emphasizing tribal engagement with broader struggle for ideological leadership this paper challenges interpretation that shows that tribal participation is episodic and externally driven. It highlights the emergence of a shared ethical framework that link tribals with national movement. This study provides more nuanced

understanding of tribal participation in national movement through hegemony.

Ultimately, the Gandhian encounters with tribal Maharashtra shows how nationalism could operate as an ethical process, where the political mobilization of tribal communities was sustained through moral legitimacy. This perspective enriches the historiography of the freedom movement and offers a valuable framework for rethinking the relationship between **nationalism**, **subaltern societies** such as tribal communities and **hegemony** in colonial India.

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9. Ibid., Pg.585.
10. Ibid., Pg.685.
11. Ibid., Pg.597.
12. Ibid., Pg.685.
13. Ibid., Pg.421.
14. Ibid., Pg. 525.
15. Ibid., Pg. 951.
16. Ibid., Pg. 909.

Endnote:

1. * Organic Intellectuals - Antonio Gramsci defines "organic intellectuals" as individuals, leaders, activist who came from specific social groups and they organize, spread, give direction to ideas in society. See Antonio Gramsci, *Selections from the Prison Notebooks*, ed. Quintin Hoare and trans. Geoffrey Nowell Smith (New York: International Publishers, 1992), Pg. 15-16
2. # Chanda means today's Chandrapur District